

The state of production of construction materials in Uzbekistan and prospects

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Abstract: This is the state of production of construction materials in Uzbekistan and prospects is one of the pressing issues at the state level today. It is said that their optimization is especially important in solving these problems

Key words: building materials, economic reforms dredging, building materials industry, raw materials material base, facilities, economical technology

Uzbekistan in the Republic brand new many residence, community, industry, village construction buildings and facilities set up reached wide scale maintenance works in progress.

In our country the first President Islam Karimov under the leadership of creativity the scope of work has expanded, the demand for building materials and their production volume more and more is increasing. Today the city in our villages done being increased huge the results of construction works are wide and smooth roads, modern bridges, high quality Majestic structures and buildings with solutions, comfortable houses, embodying our national values its expression in the embodied koshanas is finding This is the way of life of our people, life and to live condition that it is fundamentally changing is evidence.

Our country 2009 of the leader year Adopted on August 3 "Housing in rural areas with the decision on additional measures to expand the scale of

construction modern houses being built on the basis of model projects in all regions of our country places our villages appearance update, from the city less did not happen conditions in creating important factor is happening. 2013 in in places sample projects based on alone in order More than 2,500 houses have been put into use, raw materials and materials necessary for construction to prepare specialized 155 new enterprise the work started of this is a clear proof. Quality production of traditional building materials on a scientific basis, their creation technologies time requirements fit, cheap, thrifty and good quality items and technology development, assembled in enterprises from waste again getting new and thorough materials, to create their cost-effective technologies, buildings and constructions methods of repair and reconstruction perfection, and this Tasks such as efficient use of materials in the process are among the most important issues occupies

March 24, 2005 of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. F-3586 "Economic reforms deepening and construction materials industry development in the decree on "acceleration". further deepening and construction of economic reforms materials industry development acceleration main directions as construction mastering and introducing new modern technologies of material production shown.

This is it in the decree construction materials work release size increase, their development of types, mastering and application of new modern technologies, construction rational placement of material-producing capacities in the territories of the Republic was envisaged, according to which a total of 120 projects were implemented during 2005-2010 increased.

Our republic has sufficient mineral and raw material resources for the building materials industry is rich, and now more than 500 deposits of raw materials have been identified. in the Central Asian region construction materials work release for raw material reserves according to our country takes the leading place. Enriching the consumer market with modern building materials, to him to develop the industry by our state in order to meet the existing demand and need separately attention is paid.

Including to these example by doing Tashkent in the region "entUz" joint enterprise by soft short-sighted materials, Bukhara in the region to the world famous Knauf The company's technology capacity is 20 per year million m² was modern to technologies based on automated.

Cardboard products and dry construction starting the production of mixtures, In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the capacity is 1 million per year. tons of cement production giving "Rahnamo-Nur" Uzbekistan-America joint company build, Navoi capacity in the region is 12 mln. m² glass production organization in Tashkent city "Italceramica" company with in cooperation ceramic granite the product work release organize to do the project done increase such as example can be made. This things special recognition of the role of the joint-stock company "Ozkhurilishmaterialari" in the implementation it is necessary to The construction facilities of our country, the construction market of our Republic are local raw materials estimate with high-quality, modern building materials made from materials, ex'ort size to increase service in doing this of the company separately place there is

25% of the total cost of material resources in capital construction near concrete and reinforced concrete to constructions topgpri will come. This the price of other building structures and from the volume much is high. Concrete and reinforced concrete opzine physical mechanic features, endurance and work in release technical and economic efficiency and hom material the highest in capital construction now and in the future with sufficient resources has potential stuck construction material is covered remains.

Current at the time In our republic reinforced concrete constructions gpovak aggregator based preparation of lightweight concrete is required. For example, armotcement constructions, gpovak (cellular) and aerated concrete. These are known amount constructions relief issues solution is doing Constructions To save the amount of lightening fittings and cement, the section of constructions is kopndalang decrease and them prolyotin to extend take will come. Seismic forces under the influence eased constructions separately important has they are dynamic to a certain extent forces he stopped.

Capital and in general construction main matter, this do not gather iron concrete improvement of production and coating of constructions , improvement of quality and covering scientific and technical achievements in construction. Concrete technology in solving these issues improvement, his properties improve, new efficiency high stuck concretes preparation and application, mainly lightweight, high-strength woven, chemical production of compacted concrete quality increase, qualified personnel preparation, them basics of concrete science, production and technological of reinforced concrete structures accounts deep with foundations introduction is of great importance.

Looking at the prospect of production and use of reinforced concrete products out the following is the main one the closures can be highlighted:

- Big large size construction and create items and of them use;
- High to strength have and in advance oppressed from concrete use;
- Light concrete and thin walled spatial from constructions wider use;
- Products the cost decrease

Monolithic buildings and structures in the construction complex of developed countries reinforced concrete based on set up reach current is a matter Monolithic construction system reinforced concrete item and constructions from before prepared desired in the form of unified do not gather to the molds characteristic with pouring.

Monolith method building and structures when built construction time is shortened, assembly works sharp decreases, of the building strength increases construction in the field to the warehouse necessity does not click.

Current heavy metal molds per day instead of lightly cooked from metal and fiberglass collapsible universal of molds use monolithic construction system more development the reason is happening.

In the dry hot climate of Uzbekistan monolithic concrete casting is separate events done increase requirement does. In this transportation of concrete mix, molding, especially to maintenance work it is necessary to give special importance. Car covers, airfield covers and that's it such as surface big reinforced concrete monolithic constructions in construction concrete care for Don't give up materials (polyethylene, polypropylene film and etc.) bro film harvest polymers (ethinol varnish, gel polymers) is used.

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